

GloBIAS in-person workshop 2024

Set-up and general aim

The first in-person workshop of the GloBIAS initiative took place November 5, 2024 - Nov 8, 2024 in Gothenburg, Sweden.

The **aim of the workshop** was to start creating the GloBIAS scientific society:

- building a community
- connecting people and
- enabling them to exchange ideas and experiences.

The workshop was underpinned by support from the *Centre for Cellular Imaging, Core Facility*. University of Gothenburg and additional funding received from the *Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI)* (*grant number 2023-321238*). 12 attendees were supported with travel grants also remunerated by CZI. Total attendee number was 50 people from across the globe:

Overview of countries attendees of the workshop came from (based on their work location).

The scientific organisers for this workshop were Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez, Elnaz Fazeli, Rafael Camacho, Rocco D'Antuono, Kota Miura, Christa Walther, Sebastian Munck, Hanneke Okkenhaug.

Sessions

- [Session 1: Building the GloBIAS society: interfacing with other networks/associations \(networking\) - Co-Chairs: Christa Walther & Julia Fernandez Rodriguez](#)
- [Session 2: Learning how to work on projects \(budgeting resources and time\) - Chair Jean-Yves Tinevez](#)
- [Session 3: Bioimage infrastructures, tools, and data - Co-Chairs: Sebastian Munck & Tatiana Woller](#)
- [Session 4: Precision and errors in bioimage analysis \(practical\) - Co-Chairs: Rocco D'Antuono & Ana Stojiljkovic](#)
- [Session 5: Career paths and development: examples of career progression \(personal growth\) - Co-chair: Hanneke Okkenhaug & Eleonora Perego](#)
- [Session 6: Benchmarking session - Chair: Rafael Camacho](#)
- [Session 7: Bioimage analysis workflows \(practical\) - Chair: Kota Miura](#)
- [Session 8: Bioimage training curriculum session \(practical\) - Co-Chairs: Elnaz Fazeli & Christian Tischer](#)

In the following sections, we provide an overview of the aims and outcomes of the different sessions held at the workshop. Several of the presentations given are also available on the GloBIAS YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@GloBIAS/playlists>

Session 1: Building the GloBIAS society: interfacing with other networks/associations (networking)

Chairs: **Christa Walther** & Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez

(**BOLD** indicates author for subsection)

Aim

Introducing the ideas behind GloBIAS, explain where we stand at the moment with respect to the milestones of the grant, and give an outlook into the future. In addition, we look at how other BioImage Analyst networks are organised and which challenges local communities face when networking.

Outcome Report

The session started with a retrospective on NEUBIAS and how this initiative led to the idea behind GloBIAS, followed by an update on the state of the GloBIAS initiative and an introduction to the freshly founded GloBIAS association.

In the following three talks we gained insight into how community building in different countries and networking environments can work and what difficulties might be

encountered and how to overcome them. We also discussed in more detail what forms a bioimage analysts and how this formation depends on a strong and well-connected community.

Session 2: Learning how to work on projects (budgeting resources and time)

Chair: **Jean-Yves Tinevez**

Aim

The session will describe how to work on bioimage analysis projects within the scope of service facilities.

Topics:

- Welcome, goal, what to expect and with whom? Speaker introduction.
- What is behind the word 'project'? Different levels of bioimage analysis in a collaboration: access, training, consultations, collaborative projects.
- Statistics on projects. How much time / effort do they take? What can we learn from these statistics?
- The tools of project management.
- Billing and allocating resources.
- Patterns and pitfalls when providing bioimage analysis services.

Outcome Report

We had a great time with an intense exchange between the panel and the attendees. The topic, rather focused on people working in core facilities, apparently resonated with many of us.

There were intense discussions about what kind of services a core facility can provide. We challenged what was their added-value to the user, and reviewed who was providing them or not. Surprisingly, we all agreed on the importance of bioimage analysis services, but there is a wide diversity in how these services are delivered in practice. This diversity appears at all scales: specific services are delivered by some facilities and skipped by others entirely, based on identified needs. The management of projects relies on tools differing from one location to another, and the small details in what defines a bioimage analysis project turn out to be crucial. Importantly, we noticed a wide range of models when it comes to supporting bioimage analyst positions financially and billing approaches used. Clearly, this round-table helped us realize how important it would be for bioimage analysts working in core facilities to organize themselves in a workgroup, to discuss core-facility good practices in a focused context.

Session 3: Bioimage infrastructures, tools, and data

Chairs: **Sebastian Munck** & Tatiana Woller

Aim

The bioimage infrastructures, tools, and data session aims to highlight the importance of advanced infrastructures for bioimage analysis and will feature novel tools for analyzing and managing bioimage data, which is crucial for understanding complex biological processes at the cellular and molecular levels.

Infrastructures define the backbone of bioimaging research. In bioimage analysis, infrastructure comes in various forms and encompasses advanced microscopy facilities, computational resources, and collaborative networks. We will discuss the establishment, maintenance, and interconnection of these infrastructures and how they can be leveraged to enable researchers to gain deeper insights into biological systems.

Moreover, the session emphasizes the significance of data management and sharing in bioimaging research. Participants will be introduced to best practices for organizing and storing large-scale bioimage datasets, as well as the importance of data standardization and open-access repositories for facilitating collaboration and reproducibility in the scientific community.

Overall, we will aim to provide participants with not only a comprehensive overview but also foster a collaborative and interdisciplinary environment to empower researchers with the tools and expertise needed to drive innovation and discovery in the field of bioimaging.

Outcome Report

During the Bioimage infrastructures, tools, and data session, we discussed the importance of advanced infrastructures for bioimage analysis, research data management, and tools. As such, the session was conceived to link the discussion about tools with the discussion about infrastructure. Here, we felt that compute and storage infrastructure, as well as research data management, are interconnected topics but are by far more neglected. During the session, we showcased our approach to high-performance computing and its connection to research data management. Importantly I want to give a shout-out to Flanders Biomaging and the people who made that possible, namely the people from the Flemish Supercomputing Center, my colleague Benjamin Pavie, and foremostly, my co-chair Tatiana Woller.

We discussed different computing possibilities, including the opportunity to run image analysis on OpenOnDemand with a graphical user interface on a virtual desktop, which we also demonstrated live. Other topics included the data journey from the device, including storage, metadata, and our iRODs client and metadata schema manager Mango.

Next, to present our environment, we invited colleagues onto the stage to discuss their infrastructure setup. These included Anna Klemm from Upsala, Rafael Camacho from Gothenburg, Rocco D'Antuono from London, Jean-Yves Tinevez from Paris, and Robert Haase from Leipzig. These colleagues described their infrastructure environment and the level of their engagement in that. The purpose here was to show that there are different strategies and different levels of engagement depending on the underlying strategy. We finished with some ad hoc queries to the audience, about the image analysis tools they use, and high-performance computing, which are summarized below. Overall, the session triggered a number of follow-up discussions and set up further collaborations to develop best practices for image analysis in high-performance computing.

To which extent are you using commercial and open source software for analysis? Please choose what fits the best.

What open source software are you using the most?

What other open source software are you using (not Napari, Fiji, cell profiler, QuPath, icy, Jupityer, Python)?

37 responses

What commercial software do you use the most

Do you have access to high performance computing?

Are you using High performance computing?

Are courses for image analysis on high performance computing missing?

Would solutions like BAND, Open OnDemand, etc help the adoption of use of HPC in our community?

What is keeping you from using HPC?

51 responses

Session 4: Precision and errors in bioimage analysis (practical)

Chairs: **Rocco D'Antuono** & Ana Stojiljkovic

Aim

Bioimage analysis is the discipline that uses quantitative bioinformatic tools to analyse images obtained by biological experiments. For a long time, biology has been both a descriptive discipline, classifying species in the different domains of life, and a mechanistic investigation of how biomolecules, cells, and organisms function.

However, the use of quantitative methods, such as imaging, is imperative for the correct description of biological mechanisms. Recent developments of microscopy and more computational technologies have enabled the acquisition of increasingly larger and complex data sets that are suitable to answer fundamental biological questions.

In this regard, there is a need for reliable methods to quantify high-dimensional data and assess the precision and errors of the used quantification algorithms.

Focus has been put on developing a large variety of algorithms to segment, register, track, and extract quantitative information from images, but workflows aiming at proving the correctness and validity of the obtained results are far behind in this development process. Often software is mainly evaluated based on speed and throughput of individual tools rather than overall precision and error.

This session aims to address this gap by presenting validation workflows and statistical methods to assess precision and errors in bioimage analysis workflows.

Outcome Report

During the Precision and errors in bioimage analysis session, we first had four talks:

- Siân Culley (King's College London, United Kingdom) -
"Errors and quality metrics in super-resolution microscopy and beyond"
- Bruno Schuty (Advanced Bioimaging Unit, Montevideo, Uruguay) -
"Phasor Analysis in fluorescence lifetime imaging and spectral imaging with PhasoPy"
- Florian Lévêque (Interdisciplinary Institute for Neuroscience, Bordeaux, France) -
"A framework for evaluating the performance of SMLM cluster analysis algorithms"
- Adán Guerrero (National Autonomous University of Mexico, Cuernavaca, Mexico) -
"Resisting the Lure of P-Hacking"

The four speakers were then invited as guests during a panel discussion, where we asked the following questions:

1. What are the fundamental skills that a bioimage analyst should necessarily possess to ensure that BIA results are obtained with the necessary precision and minimal error?
2. What are the best metrics for segmentation, tracking, object classification that you deem fundamental?
3. What disciplines should be part of a curriculum for every image analyst? E.g. mathematics, statistics, physics, computer science, biology?
4. Are there specific hardware and infrastructures for benchmarking that every bioimage analyst should have access to?
5. How to find the right balance between accurate results in BIA and the need to work on several projects at the same time? Do you have criteria for deciding whether it is necessary to go back to the microscope/ data acquisition?

During the live discussion, we wondered how much a bioimage analyst should be involved in scientific project timeline. Of course, on one hand this depends whether a co-authorship is agreed upon. But in general, we agreed that it is difficult to find the balance to accommodate user wishes and find the criteria to decide to send them back to the microscope when the data quality is too poor. A core facility should offer courses in sample preparation and support the users to make the best out of their samples.

Here, as GloBIAS, we can put more effort into making more BIA courses available in other languages than English, so that the users feel at ease, but at the same time they can share knowledge across communities.

There was much more controversy when it came to discussing whether the bioimage analysts should point out weaknesses in the statistical approach adopted in imaging projects. Some think this is not part of our duties, some believe that statistics should belong to the basic knowledge of a bioimage analyst, as part of a broader background in science. To conclude, the session included four speakers who discussed metrics and error measurements for bioimage analysis and addressed some of the common concerns of the community about the need of quantitative methods and statistics, to support scientific reproducibility.

Session 5: Career paths and development: examples of career progression (personal growth)

Chairs: **Hanneke Okkenhaug** & Eleonora Perego

Aim

Exploring career paths and personal development for bio-image analysts. Illustrated by a number of “real-life examples”, this session will explore the career path and personal career development of the bio-image analyst. Is there such a thing as a typical bio-image analyst career path? What are the skills you need to master? Are there essential personality traits or qualities that define a bio-image analyst? Join us for this interactive session to discuss these questions and more. All workshop participants are invited to submit a short paragraph on their personal career paths, and how they feel skills learnt on the way now contribute to their jobs.

Outcome Report

Loosely based on Charles Dickens’s ‘A Christmas Caro’l, the “Career Paths and Personal Development for Bio-image Analysts” session was structured as three blocks, i.e. the Past, the Present, and the Future. Each block was introduced by a panel of two image analysts, who briefly discussed their own personal professional journeys. The discussion was then opened to the floor.

As part of the discussion, we explored whether there are such things as the “typical image analyst career path” and the “typical image analyst”. The consensus among the participants was that career paths in this field are highly diverse, with image analysts coming from backgrounds in biology, physics, engineering, and computer science.

What's your background?

Whilst the majority of the workshop participants are based in academia - either as a PI, postdoc, PhD student or in a core facility setting (imaging/image analysis), a small number are in industry or consultancy roles.

Next, the discussion explored the following questions: What are the skills you need to master? Are there essential personality traits or qualities that define a bio-image analyst? The participants commented that it was unfortunate that you could only post a single answer to this MENTI question, as it was really an “all of the above” kind of question.

Which other field did you had to explore for your position?

Session 6: Benchmarking session

Chair: **Rafael Camacho**

Aim

In the evolving field of bioimage analysis, benchmarking and testing the performance of algorithms and pipelines are paramount. As researchers, users and developers, ensuring the efficiency and accuracy of our methods is essential for advancing scientific understanding and technological innovation.

During this workshop session, we will delve into three key areas:

Benchmarking at the algorithm level (target audience – Developers): We'll explore various methodologies for testing and comparing the efficiency of different algorithms tackling similar tasks. By understanding the nuances of algorithm performance, we can make informed decisions about their suitability for specific applications.

Benchmarking at the workflow level (target audience – Analysis/Researchers): We'll discuss strategies for assessing the efficiency and accuracy of BIAs pipelines. Through case studies and real-world examples, we'll discuss best practices for evaluating pipeline performance and identifying areas for improvement.

Community-driven benchmarking practices: Together, we'll brainstorm and propose benchmarking practices tailored to our community's needs. By standardizing evaluation criteria and sharing benchmarking strategies, we can foster collaboration, accelerate innovation, and raise the overall quality of image analysis research.

During our discussion we will not only focus on performance, we'll explore ancillary topics such as ease of installation, required expertise level, and hardware considerations, to provide a holistic view of benchmarking in image analysis.

[\[2206.01653\] Metrics reloaded: Recommendations for image analysis validation \(arxiv.org\)](#)

LENA MAIER-HEIN and ANNIKA REINKE German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ)
Heidelberg, Division of Intelligent Medical Systems and HI Helmholtz Imaging

Outcome Report

The session began with a presentation by Jianxu Chen (Leibniz-Institut für Analytische Wissenschaften – ISAS – e.V., Dortmund, Germany), which provided an insightful introduction to the topic of benchmarking in bioimage analysis. His talk covered benchmarking practices within his research group, participation in international challenges, and how these experiences as a developer have shaped his perspectives on benchmarking methodologies.

Jianxu presented a case study on benchmarking a bioimage analysis workflow designed to investigate early gastrulation in *Drosophila* embryos. He demonstrated how integrating cell segmentation, tracking, and event detection can provide new insights into tissue morphogenesis. His discussion highlighted the importance of benchmarking at different stages of an analysis pipeline and the challenges associated with ensuring reproducibility, robustness, and usability in image analysis workflows.

The presentation was followed by a structure discussion round on a range of topics.

Benchmarking at algorithm level

The first discussion focused on benchmarking at the algorithm level. Participants explored the evolving landscape of benchmarking metrics across different domains based on the background of the participants (e.g. segmentation, denoising, localization microscopy, etc.). The discussion highlighted the increasing role of containerized environments, in enabling reproducible and scalable benchmarking efforts. The BioImage-Model-Zoo (<https://bioimage.io/>) initiative was recognized for its valuable work in formalizing the sharing and thus allowing comparison of deep-learning models for bioimage analysis. Competitions and challenges were also emphasized as key drivers of progress, fostering both methodological advancements and community engagement.

One of the central insights from this discussion was that

- ease of installation,
- documentation,
- and community support

are often just as critical as raw performance when it comes to the adoption of new algorithms. Methods that are widely used are not necessarily those with the highest theoretical performance but rather those that are accessible and well-supported by their respective user communities.

Benchmarking at workflow level

The second discussion addressed benchmarking at the workflow level. While algorithm-level benchmarking is better established, there remains a need for tools that help end-users assess the performance of entire analysis workflows. The discussion underscored the importance of interactivity in benchmarking tools, ensuring that non-expert users can explore and evaluate pipeline outputs effectively. There was also emphasis on developing mechanisms to detect and flag "out-of-control" cases, where pipelines fail to perform as expected. Participants agreed that such cases should be easily identifiable so that users can either improve their workflows or exclude unreliable results from studies. User experience, robustness, and accuracy emerged as the primary concerns for researchers applying bioimage analysis workflows to their data.

Community-driven benchmarking practices

The final discussion focused on community-driven benchmarking practices. While benchmarking frameworks for individual algorithms are better established in publications introducing new methods, workflow-level benchmarking remains an open challenge and an opportunity for development. Participants discussed the need for systems that assess entire workflows, allowing researchers to evaluate both performance and reliability systematically. One proposed direction was the development of visualization-based approaches, where users could inspect segmentation results, identify outliers, and use this feedback to refine workflows. Another key point was the role of automated uncertainty detection, where tools could flag regions of an image where the analysis pipeline is less confident, enabling users to make informed decisions about data inclusion.

Conclusion

The session successfully fostered deep discussions on the state of benchmarking in bioimage analysis, covering both algorithm-level and workflow-level approaches. Attendees gained insights into existing tools and methodologies, identified gaps and opportunities for community-driven benchmarking efforts, and engaged in active discussions that promoted new collaborations. The session reaffirmed the importance of developing accessible, interactive, and standardized benchmarking frameworks to ensure the reliability and reproducibility of bioimage analysis workflows.

Session 7: Bioimage analysis workflows (practical)

Chair: **Kota Miura**

Aim

This session is dedicated to the study of bioimage analysis (BIA) workflows used in life science publications. Participants are divided into several groups and are notified of their assigned group two months before the workshop (on September 1, 2024). Each group is assigned a life science paper that incorporates bioimage analysis and is tasked with attempting to reproduce the workflow described in the study. A key aspect of this session is engagement with the original authors of the assigned paper, which is highly encouraged to gain deeper insights into the methodology and clarify any ambiguities in the workflow. Additionally, if all group members agree, they are allowed to select an alternative paper if they encounter difficulties in accessing necessary materials or find a more relevant study. Beyond mere reproduction, groups are also encouraged to search for similar bioimage analysis workflows and discuss key differences and variations between methodologies. This

comparative approach is intended to foster a broader understanding of different strategies used in bioimage analysis and highlight potential improvements or alternative methods. At the workshop, each group will present their findings, sharing their experience with workflow reproduction, any challenges encountered, and insights gained from the process. Group members are expected to be well-prepared to answer questions related to the workflow and engage in discussions with other participants. The knowledge generated from this session is expected to contribute to a publication supported by GloBIAS, with authorship credited to the group members who studied each workflow in detail. By documenting these workflows systematically, the session aims to enhance reproducibility, transparency, and accessibility in bioimage analysis within the life sciences.

Outcome Report

The table below provides an overview of the papers assigned to each group. In some cases, groups were unable to establish contact with the authors of their assigned papers or were unable to obtain the necessary materials for reproduction studies, such as code and sample image data. When this occurred, alternative papers were assigned to allow the groups to continue their work.

One of the practical challenges encountered during the group work was the difference in time zones among team members, which made it difficult to schedule online meetings. Coordination across multiple time zones required flexibility, and in some cases, members had to work asynchronously, which may have affected collaboration efficiency. Another challenge was the unequal distribution of computational resources among participants. Some analyses required intensive computation, which placed a disproportionate burden on the few members who had access to powerful computing resources. This discrepancy in computational capabilities meant that not all members could contribute equally to certain tasks, making workload distribution an additional hurdle.

During the final presentation session, time management issues arose, as the session organizer struggled to allocate equal time for each group. As a result, groups presenting later in the session had to rush through their presentations due to time constraints. I (Kota) sincerely apologize to these groups, as they were unable to present their work at the same pace as others.

Despite these challenges, all groups demonstrated a strong commitment to reproducing their assigned image analysis workflows. The differences in achievements across groups were not due to a lack of effort but were instead a reflection of the availability of essential materials, such as code and image data, as well as the complexity of the image analysis methods described in the selected papers, which varied significantly. Each group adapted to the challenges they faced and contributed meaningfully to the overall goal of the session.

Group	Paper	Topic
Group 1	Stern et al. 2022. Deconstructing gastrulation at single-cell resolution. <i>Current Biology</i> . 32:1861-1868.e7. doi: 10.1016/j.cub.2022.02.059 .	Gastrulation
Group 2	Gehrels et al. 2023. Curvature gradient drives polarized tissue flow in the <i>Drosophila</i> embryo. <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences</i> . 120:e2214205120. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2214205120 .	Multicellular Dynamics
Group 3	Daeden et al. 2023. Polarized branched Actin modulates cortical mechanics to produce unequal-size daughters during asymmetric division. <i>Nat Cell Biol</i> . 25:235–245. doi: 10.1038/s41556-022-01058-9 .	Cell Division
Group 4	Yamamoto et al. 2022. Probing the rules of cell coordination in live tissues by interpretable machine learning based on graph neural networks. <i>PLOS Computational Biology</i> . 18:e1010477. doi: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010477 .	Multicellular Dynamics
Group 5	Moldenhawer et al. 2022. Spontaneous transitions between amoeboid and keratocyte-like modes of migration. <i>Front Cell Dev Biol</i> . 10:898351. doi: 10.3389/fcell.2022.898351 .	Cell Shape and Migration
Group 6v1	[canceled] Wigbers et al. 2021. A hierarchy of protein patterns robustly decodes cell shape information. <i>Nat. Phys</i> . 17:578–584. doi: 10.1038/s41567-021-01164-9 .	Cell Shape and Protein Localization
Group 6v2	[canceled] Sitarska et al. 2023. Sensing their plasma membrane curvature allows migrating cells to circumvent obstacles. <i>Nat Commun</i> . 14:5644. doi: 10.1038/s41467-023-41173-1 .	cell surface curvature
Group 6v3	Bingham et al. 2023. Presynapses contain distinct actin nanostructures. <i>Journal of Cell Biology</i> . 222:e202208110. doi: 10.1083/jcb.202208110 .	synapse structure, super resolution
Group 7v1	[canceled] Fisch et al. 2024. Molecular definition of the endogenous Toll-like receptor signalling pathways. <i>Nature</i> . 631:635–644. doi: 10.1038/s41586-024-07614-7 .	Protein interactions

Group 7v2	Villars et al. 2023. DeXtrusion: automatic recognition of epithelial cell extrusion through machine learning in vivo. Development. 150:dev201747. doi:10.1242/dev.201747.	cell extrusion analysis
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Group 1

- Gaby Martins (Lead)
- Haydee Hernández
- YaJun Wu
- Lachlan Whitehead
- Daniel Waiger

Group 1 worked on reproducing a complex and computationally intensive workflow designed to map single-cell dynamics during *Drosophila* gastrulation. The workflow involved several key steps: first, the fly embryo was segmented, and the 3D image data was projected onto a 2D surface, a process known as "pullback." Cell tracking was then conducted on this 2D projection. The resulting tracking data was subsequently mapped back onto the 3D model, enabling a detailed analysis of cellular behaviors, including cell division subgraphing and intercalations. To accomplish this, the workflow utilized a range of computational tools, including Fiji, MATLAB, ilastik, and C++ program based on ITK. Group 6 successfully reproduced many critical steps of the workflow up to the 2D projection cell tracking stage. However, some later steps were not fully replicated due to constraints in computational power and limited time. In addition to reproducing the existing workflow, the group explored alternative approaches using MorphographX and napari, experimenting 3D cell segmentation, also comparing the performance of two different models within the 3D CellPose framework. These trials and discussions provided valuable insights into potential improvements and alternative methodologies for single-cell tracking during embryonic development.

Group 2

- Caterina Fuster Barceló (Lead)
- Mélodie Ambroset
- Adan Guerrero
- Cesar Augusto Valades Cruz
- Libert Brice TONFACK
- Rocco D'Antuono

Group 2 worked on an image analysis task aimed at measuring changes in the curvature of the *Drosophila* embryo and the associated tissue flow during development. The workflow was conceptually straightforward, integrating multiple analytical approaches, including segmentation, manual tracking, particle image velocimetry (PIV), circular intensity profiling,

and physical modeling. However, the reproducibility of the analysis was significantly hindered by insufficient computational and methodological resources.

Segmentation was originally performed using a U-Net model. However, the specific model used in the original study was unavailable, along with crucial details such as parameter settings, the U-Net architecture, and an adequate set of training data. As a result, the group relied on pre-segmented images rather than training and applying the model themselves. Beyond segmentation, the challenges in re-analysis extended to all downstream steps. The absence of key workflow details, including region-of-interest (ROI) selections and specific parameters used in the original study, further impeded the group's ability to replicate the analysis. Consequently, the group was unable to fully evaluate the effectiveness of the workflow described in the paper.

Group 3

- Anna Klemm (Lead)
- Bruno Schuty
- Cheng-Yu Huang
- John Lim
- Ana Stojiljkovic
- Wojciech Jesionek

Group 3 worked on reproducing an image analysis workflow to study asymmetric cell division in Sensory Organ Precursor (SOP) cells from the thorax of *Drosophila* during the pupal stage. The goal of this analysis was to investigate the correlation between asymmetric division and actin dynamics within the cell cortex. To achieve this, various analytical techniques were employed, including cell volume measurements, cell cortex thickness analysis, actin density quantification, and Fluorescence Recovery After Photobleaching (FRAP) analysis to assess actin dynamics in different cortical regions. Among these approaches, the group specifically focused on measuring asymmetric cell volume and cell cortex thickness in SOP daughter cells.

A major challenge in reproducing the workflow stemmed from the fact that the original authors did not respond to requests for the raw image data and analysis codes, despite explicitly stating in the paper that these resources were "available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request." In the absence of these materials, the group devised a workaround by generating sample images simulating asymmetric cell volumes during mitosis. Additionally, they utilized bacterial cell fluorescence images to test and validate methods for measuring cell cortex thickness.

During their investigations, the group encountered significant issues with the Gaussian fitting approach used in the original paper for thickness measurements. Specifically, the method was found to be problematic when intensity differences existed between the inside and outside of the cell cortex. To address this limitation, the group developed alternative strategies to improve the accuracy of their measurements.

Despite the lack of access to essential data and workflow details, the group made a commendable effort to reproduce and critically evaluate the analysis, adapting their approach to overcome key obstacles.

Group 4

- Martin Schätz (Lead)
- Nicholas Wedige
- Ko Sugawara
- Felipe Delestro
- Nicole Salgado

Group 4 explored a research paper investigating the mechanisms by which multicellular coordination maintains the structure of the epidermal layer, despite the continuous processes of cell division and delamination. To analyze these dynamics, the study employed cell tracking data analyzed by training Graph Neural Network (GNN). In this approach, individual cells were treated as nodes, while their relationships with neighboring cells and their movement over time were represented as spatial and temporal edges, respectively. To enhance the predictive power of the GNN, each node (cell) was assigned additional features, including cell size and G1-phase marker fluorescence intensity. The analysis followed a reductionist strategy, in which the accuracy of predicting a cell's fate—whether it would divide, delaminate, or remain unchanged—was evaluated by systematically modifying the model's input features. Specifically, the researchers:

1. Compared predictive accuracy across models with and without additional node features.
2. Varied the size of the neighboring region considered in the analysis to assess the impact of local cellular context on fate determination.

Additionally, the findings from the GNN analysis were validated through numerical simulations of the inferred cell-cell relationships. As a post-cell tracking analysis strategy, this approach is novel and attractive not limited to this domain of study.

The resources required for reproducing the post-cell tracking analysis were publicly available and accessible online. However, several challenges arose due to poor organization of the provided scripts:

- The repository contained up to 11 layers of nested subfolders, making it difficult to locate essential scripts.
- Documentation was insufficient, further complicating navigation.
- Critical Dockerfile and requirements.txt files were missing, preventing straightforward installation of necessary software dependencies.

Due to these issues, reconstructing the workflow proved to be highly challenging. Despite these difficulties, the group managed to execute parts of the workflow successfully.

However, the location of key output files remained unclear, creating additional confusion.

Given more time and effort, it might have been possible to fully reproduce the analysis. However, by the time of the GloBIAS workshop, the group had reached the limits of their available resources and capacity.

Group 5

- Esteban Miglietta (Lead)
- Arianna Ravera
- Shaw-Chun (Peggy) Hsu
- Agustin Corbat
- Hernán Andrés Morales-Navarrete

Group 5 focused on reproducing the image analysis of migratory behavior in *Dictyostelium* cells, specifically investigating the spontaneous switching of migratory modes between two distinct forms: fan-shaped, keratocyte-like migration and amoeboid migration.

The original research paper examined these mode-switching behaviors by analyzing experimental data and qualitatively comparing it to numerical simulations of cell migration. This comparison led to insights into the potential biochemical parameters influencing the switching system. In particular, the study suggested that the observed migratory switching might be governed by a noisy bistable reaction-diffusion system, which regulates the formation of stable or unstable intracellular actin waves—key determinants of cell shape and movement.

To analyze the morphological transitions during migration, the original study utilized a modified active contour algorithm to track detailed changes in the cell's contour over time. This tracking was performed both for experimental data of migrating cells and simulated cell migration data.

Group 5's attempt to reproduce the measurement of experimental results was relatively straightforward, primarily because the active contour algorithm had already been implemented in a Python program called "Amoepy". This software, designed with a well-structured graphical user interface (GUI), facilitated the analysis and made it accessible to users without extensive coding expertise.

However, despite the ease of using Amoepy itself, some key preprocessing steps required before feeding time-lapse image data into the software were not well-documented in the original study. To address this gap, Group 5 made efforts to devise appropriate preprocessing workflows, ensuring that the input images were correctly formatted for analysis.

Group 6

- Laura Rodriguez de la Ballina (Lead)
- Rensu Theart
- Ofra Golani
- Paúl Hernández-Herrera

- Florian LEVET Levét

Group 6 faced significant difficulties in identifying a suitable research paper for their assignment due to accessibility issues with original image analysis data and code. The first paper assigned, Wigbers et al. (2021), did not provide public access to image analysis data and custom MATLAB code, despite stating in the Nature Reporting Summary that "all experimental data analyses are done using a custom MATLAB code, which will be available upon request" and that "all data needed to evaluate the conclusions in the paper are present in the paper and/or the Supplementary Materials." However, these materials were not actually included in the corresponding sections, and the authors did not respond to requests from Group 6. Due to this lack of access, a second paper, Sitarska et al. (2023), was selected. This time, the group was able to contact the authors, but the first author was on an extended summer vacation, making it impossible to obtain the necessary data and scripts in time for their analysis.

Eventually, a third paper, Bingham et al. (2023), was chosen, and one of the corresponding authors, Christophe Leterrier, responded positively to Group 6's request. He not only provided the required materials but also shared detailed instructions for reproducing their image analysis workflow, enabling Group 6 to proceed successfully. The study by Bingham et al. investigates actin nanostructures within the presynapse using Single Molecule Localization Microscopy (SMLM). While electron microscopy (EM) and drug-treatment experiments had previously suggested the presence of various presynaptic actin structures, EM alone did not provide sufficient evidence to support these hypotheses, likely because actin structures are highly fragile and do not survive the preparation process required for EM imaging. Using SMLM, Bingham et al. successfully visualized three distinct types of actin structures: actin mesh, actin rails, and actin corrals.

The image analysis in the study relied primarily on manual annotation and human-eye recognition, due to the image resolution of nanostructure obscured at the limit of the resolution of SMLM. Although some digital image processing techniques were used to refine Regions of Interest (ROIs), most of the categorization was performed manually. Group 6 attempted to replicate this process by manually annotating and categorizing key actin structures in presynaptic images, also with the help from the original authors. However, as none of the group members were experts in neuronal image analysis, the annotations varied significantly among individuals. This variation highlighted the difficulty of translating text-based descriptions into consistent annotations, as interpretation can differ widely between observers.

Group 6's experience provides a strong impression of the importance that saving annotated ROIs separately and publishing them as supplementary material alongside the paper. This would facilitate reproducibility, enable future researchers to build upon the dataset, and support systematic machine learning-based studies to automate annotation processes. Despite facing numerous challenges in accessing the necessary materials, Group 6 made the best possible efforts and successfully reproduced parts of the image analysis workflow.

Their overall experience underscores the critical need for transparent data sharing and well-documented workflows in computational image analysis studies.

Group7

- Nicholas Condon (Lead)
- Tricia Loo
- Alessandro Felder
- Edwin Hernández-Garzón
- Hanneke Okkenhaug

Group 7 initially attempted to reproduce the image analysis workflows described in Fisch et al. (2024) by reaching out to the authors for access to the necessary materials. However, they did not receive a response. While the paper stated that all materials were accessible, the custom codes used for machine learning-based classification and local maxima detection were not publicly available. Additionally, the image sequences provided in the study were in a compressed movie format, making them unsuitable for a detailed reproduction study. Due to these limitations, the group decided to switch to an alternative paper written by Villars et al. (2023).

The study by Villars et al. focuses on cell extrusion, a process in which single cells are eliminated from a tissue. This process is closely linked to tissue shape changes and is believed to play a role in coordinating multicellular morphodynamics. The paper introduces a new image analysis tool called Dextrusion, which is designed to automatically detect and measure the positions and timing of cell extrusion events within a tissue. Unlike the first study, all necessary materials for reproducing this workflow, including code and datasets, were publicly available, allowing Group 7 to proceed with their analysis without restrictions.

Session 8: Bioimage training curriculum session (practical)

Chairs: **Elnaz Fazeli** & Christian Tischer

Aim

The Bioimage Training & Education session addresses the need for accessible, high-quality bioimage analysis (BIA) training across regions with diverse resources and expertise. This session will bring together bioimage analysts, educators, and training advocates to explore how to create and disseminate foundational BIA courses and curricula that cater to a range of educational backgrounds and regional needs.

Key topics include identifying essential content for basic BIA training, sharing strategies for “train the trainer” programs, and discussing solutions to common challenges in delivering effective bioimage analysis education worldwide. We will also brainstorm how GloBIAS can support institutions in building comprehensive, adaptable curricula that engage varied audiences, from beginners to advanced practitioners.

Through a combination of presentations, discussions, and interactive activities, we’ll collaboratively explore how GloBIAS can empower researchers and students alike by supporting institutions in establishing inclusive BIA education programs.

Outcome Report

The session engaged bioimage analysts, educators, and training enthusiasts in discussions focused on core training topics, regional challenges, and train-the-trainer methodologies with a special focus on basics in image analysis. The session consisted of invited talks from teachers and interactive discussions by using mentimeter and in small groups, each assigned a specific theme.

Most of our participants were from Biological sciences with experience in learning Bioimage analysis and teaching it, some also had taken courses in pedagogy. In their opinion, the biggest challenge identified for BIA basic training was the lack of resources and funding. Trainers mostly make their own slides combined with already available training material. Therefore, it is important to have a central place where training material in relation to specific topics in the curricula is available.

Participants preferred in-person workshops, or if possible hybrid options for delivering BIA content as well as train the trainers, as it is more interactive and easier for immediate feedback collection.

During the workshop, we identified the following resources to be helpful for BIA trainers:

- centralized curriculum,
- mentorship and support,
- training material, training manuals and train the trainer workshops,
- and funding.

